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TO ASSESS AND COMPARE THE OUTCOME OF HAMILTON ANXIETY RATING SCALE (HAM-A) AND ZUNG SELF RATING ANXIETY SCALE (ZSRAS) IN PATIENTS OF GENERALIZED ANXIETY DISORDER TAKING SERTRALINE TABLETS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Sertraline is an anxiolytic drug that inhibits the reuptake of serotonin at the presynaptic membrane and is used to treat patients suffering from Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD). Various types of scale are available for assessment of Anxiety. **Objectives:** This study is aimed at assessing and comparing the outcome of ZSRAS & HAM-A in patients of GAD taking Sertraline Oral Tablets. **Primary:** To determine efficacy of Sertraline tablet as anxiolytic effect for treatment of GAD using ZSRAS as a tool for measuring anxiety level. **Secondary:** to evaluate whether ZSRAS score can be used in place of HAM-A as screening tool as well as efficacy tool for anxiety research. **Materials and methods:** This study was carried out on 52 patients (46% Male, 54% Female) having with moderate to severe GAD (HAM-A \geq 18) without any other psychiatric disorder as per DSM- IV-TR. Patients were put on Sertraline tablet 50 mg in the morning for daily for 63 days (9 weeks). ZSRAS and HAM-A scoring were performed on day 1 (randomization visit) and day 63 (end of the study visit). ZSRAS total scores (raw scores) were converted to Anxiety Index for comparison with HAM-A scores. Anxiety index scores of screening were compared with HAM-A total scores for assessing sensitivity and specificity of ZSRAS in differentiating severe level of anxiety from moderate anxiety. ZSRAS was compared with HAM-A as efficacy assessment tool by Spearman's Rho test. Efficacy of Sertraline was assessed by comparing the ZSRAS scores of randomization visit and end of the study visit by wilcoxon paired signed rank test. **Results:** Sensitivity and specificity of ZSRAS compared with HAM-A was calculated to 60% and 93%, respectively, indicating good differentiating capacity of ZSRAS for various anxiety levels. A significant decrease was observed in the total ZSRAS score from randomization visit to end of the study visit. The correlation co-efficient of ZSRAS and HAM-A were found to be 0.736 by spearman's rho. The observed decrease in ZSRAS score was found to be significant at $P < 0.001$ by wilcoxon paired sign ranked test indicating potent anxiolytic efficacy of Sertraline. **Conclusions:** Sertraline have good efficacy in treatment of GAD. The ZSRAS scale can be used in place of HAM-A as screening tool and efficacy assessment tool in anxiety research.

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INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a physiological and behavioral state induced in animals and humans by a threat to wellbeing or survival, either actual or potential. It is characterized by increased arousal, expectancy, autonomic and neuro-endocrine activation, and specific behavior patterns. The function of these changes is to facilitate coping with an adverse or unexpected situation. Pathological anxiety interferes with the ability to cope successfully with life challenges.^[1]

There are mainly 3 factors responsible for anxiety disorder; biological factor, social factor and physiological factor.^[2] People with Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) experienced with exaggerated worry and tension, even though there is little or nothing to provoke it. They anticipate disaster and are overly concerned about health issues, money, family problems, or difficulties at work. Sometimes just the thought of getting through the day produces anxiety. GAD is diagnosed when a person worries excessively about a variety of everyday problems for at least 6 months.^[3]

Patients with GAD tend to have cognitive abnormalities that hinder their ability to effectively deal with symptoms associated with GAD and other aspects of their environment. Psychotherapy is designed to help patients to develop cognitive or behavioral strategies to be able to effectively manage both cognitive and somatic symptoms that impede normal functionality.

In addition to psychotherapies, physicians have at their disposal numerous effective pharmacologic treatments. is an anxiolytic drug that inhibits the reuptake of serotonin at the presynaptic membrane and is used to treat patients suffering from Generalized Anxiety Disorder. To diagnose or for the determination of such disorders like Anxiety, Depression, a set of Questions are established, which are very useful for the appropriate diagnosis and dispensing the proper treatment. There are multiple scale are available for assessing anxiety. For example, Hamilton anxiety scale (HAM-A), Zung self rating anxiety scale (ZSRAS), Penny state worry anxiety Questioner (PSWQ), Clinical Global Impression (CGI) instrument.

To chose a scale for assessing anxiety, it should quantitative the symptoms, it should be short and simple, and it should be available in two formats so that, the patients can indicate his own responses on a self-administered scale like Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (ZSRAS), and the observer can indicate his clinical evaluation of the patient's status on the same set of criteria like Hamilton Anxiety Scale (HAM-A).^[4]

Aim and objectives:

Present study is aimed determine efficacy of Sertraline tablet as anxiolytic effect for treatment of GAD using ZSRAS as a tool for measuring anxiety level and also comparing it with one another scale that is HAM-A answering the research question, "Is ZARAS can be used in place of HAM-A as screening tool as well as efficacy tool for anxiety research?"

Material and method-

Study Design:

The present study was designed as a multicenter, open-label; parallel, prospective, randomized clinical trial conducted under routine clinical practice conditions in primary care clinic, in subjects diagnosed with GAD according to DSM-IV-TR criteria.

Patient population & data collection:

Study population of this study was 52 GAD patients (both male and female) with age ranging between 18 to 65 years. All the patients were recruited from 6 sites in Gujarat and the process was confidential and anonymous. The selection of these hospitals was done based on a few considerations. The Research protocol was approved by the local Ethics Committee (EC) and Institutional Review Boards (IRB) of the respective sites.^[5]

Translation of ZSRAS:

ZSRAS was translated to the local vernacular language Gujarati from the Standard English version by the EXCELLZA clinical trial solution Pvt. Ltd. Ahmedabad, India followed by the back translation for the same. Further accuracy of translation of Questionnaire was reviewed by Psychiatricians who participated in study.

Study schedule:

Randomization visit (Day 1):

- Scale was applied and determined the scores.
- Hamilton anxiety rating scale (Ham-A) by the investigator and score should be ≥ 18 for patient enrollment.
- Zung self rating anxiety scale (ZSRAS) by patients.
- The study patients were begun taking Sertraline tablets on the visit day

Dose of treatment:

From day 1 to 63 days: the use of Sertraline tablet 50 mg in the morning daily.

End of the study treatment visit (Day 63):

- Scale was applied and determined the scores
- Hamilton anxiety rating scale (HAM-A) by investigator
- Zung self rating anxiety scale (ZSRAS) by patients.

Efficacy analysis:

Clinician improvement was assessed by a psychiatrist. Efficacy was evaluated using ZSRAS at baseline and end of study treatment. ZSRAS was also used as an outcome measure for present study.

Validation of ZSRAS:**Acceptability:**

Patients were requested to complete the Questionnaire themselves without assistance, as correctly and as completely as they could, and it was stressed that there was no right or wrong answers.

Assessment as screening tool for anxiety.

According to Hamilton's observation published in Br. J. psychiat. in 1969, Anxiety may be categorized into four severity group, from HAM-A score normal (0-9), mild (10-15), moderate (16-24), severe (25-42). As the study enrolled patients having HAM-A ≥ 18 , patients having moderate to severe anxiety, we decided to check whether ZSRAS can also differentiate patients having severe anxiety from moderate anxiety as per HAM-A score. ^[6]

$$\text{Anxiety Index}^{[4]} = \frac{\text{Total score (raw score)} \times 100}{80}$$

Concurrent validity:

Concurrent validity is established when the scores from a new measurement procedure (ZSRAS) is directly related to the scores from a well-established measurement procedure (HAM-A) for the same construct; that is, there is consistent relationship between the scores from the two measurement procedures. This gives us confidence that the two measurement procedures are measuring the same thing.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM-SPSS for Windows (Version 19.0). Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, (SPSS later modified to read Statistical Product and Service Solutions) was released in its first version in 1968 after being developed by Norman H. Nie, Dale H. Bent and C. Hadlai Hull SPSS is among the most widely used programs for statistical analysis in social science. It is used by market researchers, health researchers, survey companies, government, education researchers, marketing organizations and others.

In statistic, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (rs) is a nonparametric measure of statistical dependence between two variables. It assess how well the relationship between two variable can be described using a monotonic function. That's why Concurrent validity was evaluated by correlating ZSRAS score with HAM-A score using spearman's coefficient of correlation (rs).

ETHICS:**Independent Ethics Committee (IEC):**

Protocol and relevant documents were submitted to site specific Ethics Committees (IEC/IRB) for their review and were approved by the Ethics Committees (IEC/IRB) prior to initiation of study of respective site.

Ethical conduct of the study:

The study was conducted according to the current version of the declaration of Helsinki (Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects, Revised by 59th WMA General Assembly Seoul, October 2008), current ICH GCP guidelines, regulatory requirements of EMEA, ICMR guidelines and CDSCO guidelines.

Patient information and consent:

The Informed Consent Forms were issued to all the subjects in the language they best understand before study conduction. Doctor/ Physician explained

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

68 patients were enrolled in this study. For scale comparison, among this, 52 were only randomized and remaining 16 patients were screening failure.

Table 1: Demographic data –Age (year).

	GAD (PATIENTS)
Mean	3.90
Min	19
Max	59
SD	09.50
Median	37.50

Table 1 depicts mean±age age group of patients found to be 36.90±09.50. The age group and Gender distribution for a validation study is as represented in Figure 1. The questionnaires had high acceptability as there were no missing answers in all items of the scale filled by all the subjects. The participants did not report any difficulty in answering the questionnaire. The mean time spent was about six minutes.

Figure 1: (A) Demographic Profile for Anxiety Patients Included In Validation Study, (B) Gender Distribution of GAD patients in Validation Study.

As published by William W.K. Zung in the journal of Academy of Psychosomatic Medicine in November-December 1971, an index for the ZSRAS can be derived by dividing the sum of the values (raw score) obtained on the 20 items by the maximum possible score of 80, converted into a decimal and multiply by 100 (William W.K., 1971). Those raw score is converted in to anxiety index by given formula:

Score Range: 20-80

$$\text{Anxiety Index} = \frac{\text{Total score (raw score)} \times 100}{80}$$

Table 2: Tabular data of change in total score of HAM-A and ZSRAS.

Patient id	HAM-A (D1-D63)	ZSRAS(D1-D63)
LBA01	13	13
LBA02	16	24
LBA03	17	23
LBA04	16	21
LBA05	16	23
LBA06	18	25
LBA07	9	11
LBA08	38	43
LBA09	20	23
LBA10	19	26
LBA11	19	30
LBA12	14	20
LBA13	13	8
LBA14	9	11
LBA15	24	30
LBA16	20	32
LBA17	12	19
LBA18	12	22
LBA19	16	17
LBA20	7	9
LBA21	9	9
LBA22	24	29
LBA23	17	12
LBA24	18	11
LBA25	18	23
LBA26	16	16
LBA27	15	21
LBA28	17	20
LBA29	18	9
LBA30	16	15
LBA31	18	27
LBA32	24	29
LBA33	26	35
LBA34	19	22
LBA35	16	23
LBA36	14	30
LBA37	15	22
LBA38	15	26
LBA39	21	31
LBA40	9	14
LBA41	14	18
LBA42	0	8
LBA43	13	16
LBA44	24	24
LBA45	22	26
LBA46	29	29
LBA47	26	32
LBA48	20	32
LBA49	24	28
LBA50	17	-3
LBA51	14	9
LBA52	15	5

Figure 3: Graphical Representation of ZSRAS Anxiety Index at Randomization Visit (D1) & End of the study visit (D63).

Table: 2 and Figure:3 shows that there is reduction in anxiety index from patient LBA01 to LBA21, same as significant reduction from LBA26 to LBA49 by given anxiolytic treatment. Whereas, no significant change seen in anxiety index from patient LBA46 to LBA54. overall, the reduction in anxiety index by given anxiolytic treatment.

The Comparison total score of randomization visit and end of the study visit were undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of Sertraline in the treatment of GAD using ZSRAS showed in Table: 3. Sertraline has clearly demonstrated the good ability to control anxiety level in GAD patients. Thus the main outcome measure use in the present study was ZSRAS. There were found to be significant decrement in the anxiety index between Randomization visit & End of the study visit for Sertraline treated patient. The anxiolytics response was achieved by and a study decrease in total ZSRAS score was observed in the study period.

Table 3: Evaluation of Efficacy Sertraline Tablet Using ZSRAS Scale at Randomization visit & End of the study visit (Wilcoxon signed rank test).

	Rank	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
ZSRAS D1 – ZSRAS D63	Negative rank	51 ^a	27.00	1377.00
	Positive rank	1 ^b	1.00	1.00
	Ties	0		
	Total	52		

- A. ZSRASD1 < ZSRAS D63
- B. ZSRASD1 > ZSRAS D63
- C. ZSRASD1 = ZSRAS D63

Table 4: Test statistics ^b.

	ZSRASV1 – ZSRAS V2
Z	-6.266 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (1- tailed)	000**

**p < 0.001 level.

- a. Based on positive ranks.
- b. Wilcoxon paired signed ranks test.

By examining the final test statistics Table: 4, we find out whether these changes, due to Sertraline treatment, led overall to a statistically significant difference in total score. We are looking for the *Asymptomatic Sig.* (1-tailed) value, which in this case is 0.000. This is the p value for the test. We report the Wilcoxon signed rank test using Z statistic. It was performed to evaluate the efficacy of Sertraline tablet. Result shown that Asymp. Sig. (1- tailed) p = 0.00 at p < 0.001 level with Z statistic value -6.266.

Table 5: Cumulative Result: Comparison of mean score of both scales (ZSRAS & HAM-A) at randomization visit (D1) & end of the study visit (D63).

Score	Randomization visit (mean)	end of the study visit (mean)
ZSRAS	50.60	29.86
HAM-A	27.09	9.96

Figure 4: Cumulative Result: Comparison of mean score of both scales (ZSRAS & HAM-A) at randomization visit (D1) & end of the study visit (D63).

Results are presented for anxiolytic effect of Sertraline based on the change of total score of both scale at randomization visit & end of the study visit (Table: 5 and Figure: 4). Sertraline had an anxiolytic effect and steady decreasing in total score of both scales (ZSRAS & HAM-A) were observed throughout the study period. After end of the study visit total mean score of ZSRAS & HAM-A were 29.86 and 9.96 respectively.

Concurrent validity:

Concurrent validity was established between ZSRAS and HAM-A scales. It has been found that correlation is significant at 0.01 levels. The correlation co-efficient of 2 scales were found to be 0.736 by spearman's rho. This was shown in Table: 6.

Table 6: Nonparametric Correlations of the change in the scores of two scales (ZSRAS and HAM-A) between randomization visit (D 1) and end of the study visit (D 63).

			ZSRAS	HAM-A
Spearman's rho	ZSRAS	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.736**
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	52	52
	HAM-A	Correlation Coefficient	.736**	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	52	52

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

William Zung study demonstrated that self rating scale (ZARAS) and clinican rated scale (HAM-A) both having correlation coefficient was found to be 0.736 (Table: 6) and our present study result indicates the correlation co-efficient between change in score between randomization visit (D1) and end of the study visit (D63) of both scales (ZSRAS & HAM-A) were performed by spearman's rho test. The significant association between the sets of rank by calculating spearman's rank correlation co-efficient (rs) is indicated by $p = 0.05$, as usual. Results indicate that there is evidence to suggest good agreement ($r^2 = 0.74$) between the scale's assessment ($p = 0.00$). The result demonstrated that ZSRAS has a good ability to assess the GAD in comparison to the HAM –A scale.

CONCLUSION

It is observed that practical and conceptual difficulties in delineating specific anxiety disorder, ranging from overlap (mixed anxiety and depression) to co-morbidity between anxiety disorder, we evaluated ZSRAS as screening tool and efficacy evaluation tool in anxiety research. The ZSRAS is widely used brief self reporting scale (20 items). In this study, sensitivity and specificity of ZSRAS was calculated as 60% and 93% respectively, which indicates good differentiating capacity of ZSRAS in classifying anxiety severity. Hence, ZSRAS can be used to enroll patients with particular severity of anxiety in research study as an alternative to HAM-A. The study result indicates that Sertraline is effective in controlling anxiety symptoms as perceived by patient's rating scale (ZSRAS) as ($Z = -6.266$, $P = 0.00$) by Wilcoxon paired sign rank test. The study observations show that the changes in ZSRAS closely respond to changes in HAM-A score indicating good concurrent validity for efficacy assessment tool as assessed by Spearman's coefficient of rank correlation test (0.736, $p = 0.00$) in this study. We conclude that ZSRAS can be used as an alternative to HAM-A as patient rated anxiety evaluation scale. Choice of treatment is affected by patient's characteristics (such as previous response or contra-indications), the evidence base supporting its use, patients and physician preference, and the local availability of that proposed intervention. Sertraline was found to be effective and efficient drug therapy for the treatment of generalized anxiety disorder patients at a dose 50 mg in the morning.

Recommended Future Research:

ZARAS is a patient rated scale and HAM-A is the technician rated scale, in future one combine scale should be studied so that outcomes become more relevant in which both doctor and patient participate equally.

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

List of Abbreviation:

GAD	:	Generalized Anxiety Disorder
ZARAS	:	Zung Self Rating Anxiety Scale
HAM-A	:	Hamilton Anxiety Scale
PSWQ	:	Penny State Worry
CGI	:	Clinical Global Impression

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